

EFFECT OF SPORTS VISION TRAINING ON EYE HAND SPEED AMONG KHO KHO PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of sports vision training on eye hand speed among kho kho players. It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences on eye hand speed due to the effect of sports vision training among kho kho players. For the present study the 30 male kho kho players from Namakkal, were selected at random and their age ranged from 18 to 21 years. For the present study pre test - post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used. The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen each. Group 'A' underwent sports vision training only, group 'B' have not underwent any training. The data was collected before and after twelve weeks of training. The data was analyzed by applying 't' test. The level of significance was set at 0.05. It was observed that the six weeks of sports vision training have significantly improved the hand eye speed of kho kho players.

Key Words: Sports Vision Training, Eye Hand Speed, Kho Kho Players.

Introduction:

Sports Vision is the branch of optometry concerned with vision and perception, evaluating and enhancing visual performance, and prescribing, where necessary, the most appropriate visual aids. However, not all vision problems can be solved so simply by means of either optical correction or simple changes in posture. Some sports practitioners need to practice certain visual tasks repeatedly to improve a weakness, such as eye-hand speed, eye-foot speed etc for example. We call this work 'sports vision training. There was mist likely a vague realization that good eyesight was important in shooting an arrow, catching a ball or driving a chariot. But no one knew what to do about it, knowledge about the physiological and psychological functions of the visual system was very meager until the nineteenth century, and it was well into the twentieth before science had unveiled enough of the mysteries to begin considering improving visual performance by some kind of vision therapy (Bottoms et al. 2011).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of sports vision training on eye hand speed among kho kho players. It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences on eye hand speed due to the effect of sports vision training among kho kho players. For the present study the 30 male kho kho players from Namakkal, were selected at random and their age ranged from 18 to 21 years. For the present study pre test - post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used. The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen each. Group 'A' underwent sports vision training only, group 'B' have not underwent any training. The data was collected before and after twelve weeks of training. The data was analyzed by applying 't' test. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of 't' Ratio between the Pre Test and Post Test Means of Eye Hand Speed of Experiment Group and Control Group

S.No	Variables	Mean Diff	SD	σ DM	t' ratio
1	Eye Hand Speed	Exp:0.03	Exp:0.02	Exp:0.00	5.14*
		Con:0.00	Con:0.04	Con:0.01	0.25

*Significant at 0.05 level

An examination of table 1 indicates that the obtained 't' ratio for eye hand speed of experimental group was 5.14. The obtained 't' ratio on eye hand speed was found to be greater than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. This indicates that the Vision training had significant effect upon their performance. The obtained 't' ratios for eye hand speed of control group was 0.25. The obtained 't' ratio on eye hand speed was found to be lesser than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 9 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be not significant. The mean scores of eye hand speed of experimental group and control group was shown graphically in figure 1.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram Showing the Pre Mean and Post Mean of Eye Hand Speed of Experimental Group and Control Group

Conclusions:

- It was observed that the six weeks of sports vision training have significantly improved the hand eye speed of kho kho players.
- The experimental group had achieved significant improvement due to sports vision training and has significantly improved the hand eye speed of kho kho players when compared to control group.

References:

1. Bender, R.S (1984). The effects a vision training program has on the ball - handling skills of children with visually - related learning disabilities. Completed research, 27. 178
2. Beverley C A, Bath P A, & Booth A (2004). Health information needs of visually impaired people: a systematic review of literature. School of Health and related research. Health & social care in the community, 12:1, 1-24.
3. Bonsel, S, K., Feltgen, N., Burau, H., Hansen, L. & Bach, M. (2006). Visual acuities “hand motion “and “counting fingers” can be quantified with the Frieberg visual acuity test. Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci. 47(3):1236-40.
4. Bottoms, Lindsay M. Sinclair, Jonathan, Gabrysz, Tomas, Szmatlan-Gabrysz, Ursula, Price, Michael J. (2011). Physiological Responses and Energy Expenditure to Simulated Epee Fencing in Elite Female Fencers. Serbian Journal of Sports Sciences, 5 1, 17-20.
5. Bressan, E.S. (2003) Effects of visual skills training, vision coaching and sports vision dynamics on the performance of a sport skill. African Journal of Physical, Health Education, Recreation and Dance 9(1), 20-31.
6. Giorgi, D., Contestabile, M.T., Pacella, E. & Gabrieli, C.B. (2005). An instrument for biofeedback applied to vision. Appl Psychophysiol Biofeedback. 30(4):389-95.
7. Hurst J A (1986).Comparison of depth and visual perception with manual dexterity among educable and trainable mentally handicapped and normal boys. Completed research. 29:169
8. Johnson C.A (1986) A comparison of dynamic balance of preadolescent visually impaired and sighted males. Completed research, 27, 76.
9. Johnson DJ (1987). The role of vision in compensation for vestibular after-effects during skilled performance. Completed Research.30:92.
10. MS Kumar, AD Kumar, Effect of Mental Training on Self Confidence among Professional College Students, International Journal of Recent Research and Applied Studies, Vol 4, No. 12, 2017, 51-53
11. MS Kumar, AD Kumar, A Statistical Approach towards the Effect of Yoga on Total Cholesterol of Overweight Professional College Students, International Journal of Recent Research and Applied Studies, Vol 4, No. 2, 2017, 126-128
12. Suresh, Kumar M. (2019). Position wise assessment of body weight among novice and experienced basketball players. The International journal of analytical and experimental modal analysis, XI,XI, 526-531.

13. Suresh, Kumar M. (2019). Comparative Analysis of Core Strength among Football Hockey and Kabaddi Players. Think India Journal, 22,14, 1261-1264.
14. Sujitha Paulose & M. Suresh Kumar (2020). Effect of Progressive Muscular Relaxation Training on Selected Psychomotor Variables among Hockey Players. Alochana Chakra Journal, 9,5, 2439-2443.